

1 HSV-1 ICP22 activates SAMD9L.

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6 The HSV-1 genome contains dozens of viral gene products. We measured total transcription by
7 RNA-sequencing in human cells expressing doxycycline-inducible ICP22 to discover novel functions and
8 network interaction partners of ICP22. We describe here control of SAMD9L by ICP22.

9 Citations

10 1. Wong, J.C., Bryant, V., Lamprecht, T., Ma, J., Walsh, M., Schwartz, J., del pilar Alzamora, M.,
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12 mutations are associated with extensive genetic evolution and diverse hematologic outcomes. *JCI insight*,
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